

Supplementary Information for “A Time-Step-Based Neural Network Framework for Modeling Chaotic Dynamics in Multi-Pendulum and Biological Systems”

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S1 Derivation of Differential Equations

To derive the differential equations of motion for the double pendulum, we use the Lagrangian method, which involves expressing the system’s kinetic and potential energies in terms of the angular displacements (θ_1 and θ_2) and then applying the Euler-Lagrange equation to obtain a set of coupled second-order differential equations describing the pendulum’s motion. The double pendulum’s motion depends on three key factors: gravity, masses of pendulums m_1 and m_2 , and the lengths of pendulums L_1 and L_2 . The motion is described by the angles θ_1 and θ_2 , the angles each rod makes with the vertical axis.

The Lagrangian L is given by:

$$L = T - U$$

where T is the kinetic energy and U is the potential energy.

Kinetic Energy

The kinetic energy T for a double pendulum can be calculated by summing the kinetic energies of each mass.

For mass m_1 (the first pendulum):

1. The position in Cartesian coordinates is:

$$x_1 = L_1 \sin(\theta_1), \quad y_1 = -L_1 \cos(\theta_1)$$

2. The velocity components are:

$$\dot{x}_1 = L_1 \dot{\theta}_1 \cos(\theta_1), \quad \dot{y}_1 = L_1 \dot{\theta}_1 \sin(\theta_1)$$

3. The kinetic energy for m_1 is:

$$T_1 = \frac{1}{2} m_1 (\dot{x}_1^2 + \dot{y}_1^2) = \frac{1}{2} m_1 (L_1 \dot{\theta}_1)^2$$

For mass m_2 (the second pendulum):

The position depends on both θ_1 and θ_2 :

1. The position in Cartesian coordinates is:

$$x_2 = L_1 \sin(\theta_1) + L_2 \sin(\theta_2), \quad y_2 = -L_1 \cos(\theta_1) - L_2 \cos(\theta_2)$$

2. The velocity components are:

$$\dot{x}_2 = L_1 \dot{\theta}_1 \cos(\theta_1) + L_2 \dot{\theta}_2 \cos(\theta_2), \quad \dot{y}_2 = L_1 \dot{\theta}_1 \sin(\theta_1) + L_2 \dot{\theta}_2 \sin(\theta_2)$$

3. The kinetic energy for m_2 is:

$$T_2 = \frac{1}{2} m_2 (\dot{x}_2^2 + \dot{y}_2^2)$$

Potential Energy

The potential energy U is based on the heights of the masses relative to a reference point (usually chosen as the lowest position in the system).

Step 1: Gravitation Potential Energy For Masses:

For mass m_1 :

$$U_1 = m_1 g y_1 = - m_1 g L_1 \cos(\theta_1)$$

For mass m_2 :

$$U_2 = m_2 g y_2 = - m_2 g (L_1 \cos(\theta_1) + L_2 \cos(\theta_2))$$

The total potential energy is:

$$U = U_1 + U_2$$

Step 2: Formulating the Lagrange's Equations

Now we apply the Euler-Lagrange equation for each generalized coordinate θ_1 and θ_2 :

$$\frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{\partial L}{\partial \dot{\theta}_i} \right) - \frac{\partial L}{\partial \theta_i} = 0, \quad i = 1, 2$$

Step 3: Deriving the Equations of Motion

After computing the partial derivatives and substituting into the Euler-Lagrange equation, we obtain two coupled second-order differential equations for θ_1 and θ_2 .

The configuration vector is:

$$V = [\theta_1, u_1, \theta_2, u_2]$$

where $u_1 = \frac{d\theta_1}{dt}$ and $u_2 = \frac{d\theta_2}{dt}$.

We let:

$$c = \cos(\theta_1 - \theta_2), \quad s = \sin(\theta_1 - \theta_2)$$

and the equations become:

$$\frac{du_1}{dt} = \frac{m_2 g \sin(\theta_2) c - m_2 s (L_1 c u_1^2 + L_2 c u_2^2) - (m_1 + m_2) g \sin(\theta_1)}{L_1 (m_1 + m_2 s^2)}$$

$$\frac{du_2}{dt} = \frac{(m_1+m_2)(L_1 u_1^2 s - g \sin(\theta_2) + g \sin(\theta_1) c) + m_2 L_2 u_2^2 s c}{L_1(m_1+m_2 s^2)}$$

For triple pendulum, the equations are:

$$\begin{aligned} du1/dt &= \frac{m1(od1_1 \cdot od1_2 \cdot od1_3 \cdot r2 - 4 \cdot (-m3 \cdot od1_2 \cdot r1 + (m3 \cdot r12 + m12 \cdot r3 \cdot r2) \cdot \cos(\theta1 - \theta2)) \cdot od1_4 - (od1_5 + 4m3r12 + 4m12r3r2) \cdot od1_6}{l1 \cdot od1_7 \cdot m012 \cdot r2} \\ du2/dt &= \frac{-m3 \cdot r1 \cdot m012 \cdot od2_1 \cdot r2 - (m3 \cdot (r1 \cos(\theta1 - \theta2) + r2 \cos(\theta1 - \theta3)) \cdot r1 - (m3 \cdot r12 + m12 \cdot r3 \cdot r2) \cdot \cos(\theta1 - \theta2)) \cdot od2_2 + m012 \cdot r3 \cdot r2 \cdot od2_3}{l2 \cdot od1_7 \cdot r2} \\ du3/dt &= \frac{m12 \cdot (od1_2) \cdot (od3_1) + m12 \cdot m012 \cdot (od3_2) \cdot r2 - r1 \cdot m012 \cdot od3_3}{l3 \cdot (m3 \cdot r12 + m12 \cdot r3 \cdot r2)} \end{aligned}$$

S2 Runge-Kutta Method

The Runge-Kutta 4th Order method (RK4) is a numerical technique for solving ordinary differential equations (ODEs), thus giving it the name ODE-RK4. It provides an approximation to the solution of differential equations by calculating successive values at discrete time steps. Unlike simpler methods like Euler's method, RK4 is more accurate and is often used for systems where higher precision is required. It achieves this accuracy by taking a weighted average of slopes at multiple points within each time interval.

Given that the differential equations for the double pendulum are of second order, a 4th order method such as ODE-RK4 provides superior accuracy, enabling the smooth animations of the double pendulum that we were able to create.

Initial Value Problem

Given an initial value problem:

$$\frac{dy}{dt} = f(t, y), \quad y(t_0) = y_0$$

ODE-RK4 provides an estimate for y at a time $t + h$, where h is the time step size.

The RK4 Algorithm

The RK4 algorithm calculates the next point y_{n+1} using four intermediate "slopes" (values of f evaluated at different points):

1. Calculate k_1 : The slope at the beginning of the interval.

$$k_1 = h \cdot f(t_n, y_n)$$

2. Calculate k_2 : The slope at the midpoint, using k_1 to adjust y .

$$k_2 = h \cdot f\left(t_n + \frac{h}{2}, y_n + \frac{k_1}{2}\right)$$

3. Calculate k_3 : Another midpoint slope, using k_2 to adjust y .

$$k_3 = h \cdot f\left(t_n + \frac{h}{2}, y_n + \frac{k_2}{2}\right)$$

4. Calculate k_4 : The slope at the end of the interval, using k_3 to adjust y .

$$k_4 = h \cdot f\left(t_n + h, y_n + k_3\right)$$

Finally, update y to the next step:

$$y_{n+1} = y_n + \frac{1}{6}(k_1 + 2k_2 + 2k_3 + k_4)$$

The RK4 method improves accuracy by considering the contributions of these intermediate points.

Applying RK4 to the System

To apply RK4, we rewrite the system as a set of four first-order ODEs:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d\theta_1}{dt} &= \omega_1, & \frac{d\theta_2}{dt} &= \omega_2 \\ \frac{d\omega_1}{dt} &= f_1(\theta_1, \theta_2, \omega_1, \omega_2), & \frac{d\omega_2}{dt} &= f_2(\theta_1, \theta_2, \omega_1, \omega_2) \end{aligned}$$

Let:

$$y = [\theta_1, \theta_2, \omega_1, \omega_2]$$

For each time step h , we apply the RK4 method to each of these equations simultaneously. Through this, we obtain a solution to the differential equations: the angle measurements of the first and second pendulum.

ODE-RK4 Implementation and Timestep Calculation

ODE-RK4 runs in a loop, so for every timestep, we calculate the angle measures and store them in an array, finally displaying them as a graph. The timestep increment for calculation is determined by a , b , and n :

- a is the start time,
- b is the end time,
- n is a variable denominator to increase/decrease step size.

For example, to calculate the solutions from 0 seconds to 10 seconds:

$$a = 0, \quad b = 10, \quad n = 1000$$

The timestep increment would be:

$$\frac{b-a}{n} = \frac{10-0}{1000} = 0.01$$

To find the total number of timesteps/iterations of the ODE-RK4 method, we calculate:

$$\frac{b-a}{\text{timestep increment}} = \frac{10-0}{0.01} = 1000 \text{ timesteps.}$$

This means the for-loop for ODE-RK4 will iterate 1000 times, compiling all the θ_1 and θ_2 points into an array to graph.

Python Implementation of ODE-RK4

The Python implementation of ODE-RK4 is as follows:

```

import numpy as np
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
from math import sin, cos, pi
from numpy import array, arange, zeros_like
import torch
import torch.nn as nn
import torch.optim as optim
from sklearn.preprocessing import MinMaxScaler
from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split
from torch.utils.data import TensorDataset, DataLoader
from sklearn.metrics import mean_squared_error, r2_score

g = 9.81
L1 = 1
L2 = 1
m1 = 1.0
m2 = 1.0

def f(r, t, L1, L2):
    theta1 = r[0]
    omega1 = r[1]
    theta2 = r[2]
    omega2 = r[3]

    ftheta1 = omega1
    fomega1 = (-g * (2 * m1 + m2) * sin(theta1) - m2 * g * sin(theta1 - 2 *
theta2) - 2 * sin(theta1 - theta2) * m2 *
                (omega2**2 * L2 + omega1**2 * L1 * cos(theta1 - theta2))) /
(L1 * (2 * m1 + m2 - m2 * cos(2 * theta1 - 2 * theta2)))

    ftheta2 = omega2
    fomega2 = (2 * sin(theta1 - theta2) * (omega1**2 * L1 * (m1 + m2) + g *
(m1 + m2) * cos(theta1) + omega2**2 * L2 * m2 *
                cos(theta1 - theta2))) / (L2 *
(2 * m1 + m2 - m2 * cos(2 * theta1 - 2 * theta2)))

    return array([ftheta1, fomega1, ftheta2, fomega2], float)

a = 0.0
b = 1000
N = 3000
h = (b - a) / N
tpoints = np.arange(a, b, h)

```

```

theta1_points = np.zeros_like(tpoints)
theta2_points = np.zeros_like(tpoints)
#Initial angles
[theta1, angularvelocity1, theta2, angularvelocity2]
q = np.array([pi / 2, 0, pi / 2, 0], float)
#Runge Kutta Implementation
#Runs in a for loop for every timestep to calculate angles
for i, t in enumerate(tpoints):
    theta1_points[i] = q[0] * 180 / pi
    theta2_points[i] = q[2] * 180 / pi

    k1 = h * f(q, t, L1, L2)
    k2 = h * f(q + 0.5 * k1, t + 0.5 * h, L1, L2)
    k3 = h * f(q + 0.5 * k2, t + 0.5 * h, L1, L2)
    k4 = h * f(q + k3, t + h, L1, L2)
    q += (k1 + 2 * k2 + 2 * k3 + k4) / 6

#Theta 1 and Theta 2 (Angles of pendulum rods in relation to the vertical)
are graphed on a plot using Matplotlib

#theta1_points contains all angles for theta1 from timestep 0 to last
timestep
plt.plot(tpoints, theta1_points, label='Theta1')

#theta2_points contains all angles for theta2 from timestep 0 to last
timestep

plt.plot(tpoints, theta2_points, label='Theta2')

#Graph titles
plt.title("Double Pendulum")
plt.xlabel("t (seconds)")
plt.ylabel("degrees")
plt.legend()
plt.show()
#Save as numpy array (final dataset)
data = np.stack((theta1_points, theta2_points), axis=1)
np.save('pendulum_data.npy', data)

```

To compile a dataset for multiple initial angles, we need to use a nested for-loop with an array full of initial angles as follows:

```

import numpy as np
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
from math import sin, cos, pi
from numpy import array, arange, zeros_like
import torch
import torch.nn as nn
import torch.optim as optim
from sklearn.preprocessing import MinMaxScaler
from torch.utils.data import Dataset, DataLoader
from sklearn.metrics import mean_squared_error, r2_score

# Double Pendulum Parameters
g = 9.81
L1 = 1
L2 = 1
m1 = 1.0
m2 = 1.0

# Function for Double Pendulum System
def f(r, t, L1, L2):
    theta1 = r[0]
    omega1 = r[1]
    theta2 = r[2]
    omega2 = r[3]

    ftheta1 = omega1
    fomega1 = (-g * (2 * m1 + m2) * sin(theta1) - m2 * g * sin(theta1 - 2 * theta2)
- 2 * sin(theta1 - theta2) * m2 *
                (omega2**2 * L2 + omega1**2 * L1 * cos(theta1 - theta2))) / (L1 * (2
* m1 + m2 - m2 * cos(2 * theta1 - 2 * theta2)))

    ftheta2 = omega2
    fomega2 = (2 * sin(theta1 - theta2) * (omega1**2 * L1 * (m1 + m2) + g * (m1 +
m2) * cos(theta1) + omega2**2 * L2 * m2 *
                cos(theta1 - theta2))) / (L2 * (2 * m1 +
m2 - m2 * cos(2 * theta1 - 2 * theta2)))

    return array([ftheta1, fomega1, ftheta2, fomega2], float)

# Simulation Parameters
a = 0.0
b = 10
N = 2000
h = (b - a) / N

angles = [[120, 0], [121, 1], [120, 2], [120,4], [120,6], [120,8], [120,10],[122,
0], [122, 2], [122,4], [122,6], [122,8], [122,10],[124, 0], [124, 2], [124,4],

```

```
[124,6], [124,8], [124,10], [126, 0], [126, 2], [126,4], [126,6], [126,8],
[126,10], [128, 0], [128, 2], [128,4], [128,6], [128,8], [128,10], [130, 0], [130,
2], [130,4], [130,6], [130,8], [130,10]]
```

```
for x in angles:
    tpoints = np.arange(a, b, h)
    theta1_points = np.zeros_like(tpoints)
    theta2_points = np.zeros_like(tpoints)

    q = np.array([x[0] * pi / 180, 0, x[1] * pi / 180, 0], float)

    for i, t in enumerate(tpoints):
        theta1_points[i] = q[0] * 180 / pi
        theta2_points[i] = q[2] * 180 / pi

        k1 = h * f(q, t, L1, L2)
        k2 = h * f(q + 0.5 * k1, t + 0.5 * h, L1, L2)
        k3 = h * f(q + 0.5 * k2, t + 0.5 * h, L1, L2)
        k4 = h * f(q + k3, t + h, L1, L2)
        q += (k1 + 2 * k2 + 2 * k3 + k4) / 6

    plt.plot(tpoints, theta1_points, label='Theta1')
    plt.plot(tpoints, theta2_points, label='Theta2')
    plt.title("Double Pendulum")
    plt.xlabel("t (seconds)")
    plt.ylabel("degrees")
    plt.legend()
    plt.show()

    data = np.stack((theta1_points, theta2_points), axis=1)
    np.save(f'pendulum_data_{str(x[0])}_{str(x[1])}.npy', data)
```

The ODE-RK4 implementation of a friction-based system does not change, only the differential equations inside the function $f(r, t)$ as shown in S1.

S3 Lyapunov Exponent and Analysis

In order to determine the stability of the double pendulum system, we used 2 approaches: Lyapunov exponent and eigenvalues.

Lyapunov exponent:

The Lyapunov exponent of a system at initial condition (θ_1, θ_2) is defined as e^L which represents the rate at which small perturbations deviate from the trajectory of the initial condition. In order to do this, we found the trajectory of both (θ_1, θ_2) and $(\theta_1 + p, \theta_2)$ for 10000 timesteps, and then found the slope of the line of best fit for the natural log of the angular difference to determine if the perturbation deviated exponentially.

The code to find the Lyapunov exponent at specific initial conditions is as follows:

```
import math

initial_conditions = np.arange(0, 181, 15)
lyapunov_exponents = np.zeros((len(initial_conditions),
len(initial_conditions)))

def periodic_distance(theta1, theta2):
    delta = (theta1 - theta2)
    return np.abs(delta)

for i_1, angle_a_component in enumerate(initial_conditions):
    for j_1, angle_b_component in enumerate(initial_conditions):

        initial_condition = [angle_a_component, angle_b_component]
        delta_0 = 0.5

        angle_a = initial_condition
        angle_b = [initial_condition[0] + delta_0, initial_condition[1]]

        ## Get model predictions

        distances = []
        for i in range(len(x_unknown)):
            dist = math.sqrt(periodic_distance(y_pred_unknown_a[i, 0],
y_pred_unknown_b[i, 0]) ** 2 + periodic_distance(y_pred_unknown_a[i, 1],
y_pred_unknown_b[i, 1]) ** 2)
            distances.append(math.log(abs(dist), math.e))

        m, c = np.polyfit(np.arange(len(x_unknown)), distances, 1)

        lyapunov_exponents[i_1][j_1] = m
```

Eigenvalues:

The eigenvalues of the Jacobian matrix M are 4 scalars which describe when the linear transformation applied does not change the direction of the start point. When the eigenvalues have a positive real part, it is an unstable oscillator. On the other hand, when they are negative, the system behaves as a damped oscillator.

The code to find the eigenvalues at any initial condition of $[\theta_1, \omega_1, \theta_2, \omega_2]$ is as follows:

```

import sympy as sp
import numpy as np

theta1, omega1, theta2, omega2, L1, L2, m1, m2, g = sp.symbols('theta1 omega1
theta2 omega2 L1 L2 m1 m2 g')

def f(r):
    theta1, omega1, theta2, omega2 = r

    ftheta1 = omega1
    fomega1 = (-g * (2 * m1 + m2) * sp.sin(theta1) - m2 * g * sp.sin(theta1 - 2
* theta2) -
                2 * sp.sin(theta1 - theta2) * m2 * (omega2**2 * L2 + omega1**2 *
L1 * sp.cos(theta1 - theta2))) / \
                (L1 * (2 * m1 + m2 - m2 * sp.cos(2 * theta1 - 2 * theta2)))

    ftheta2 = omega2
    fomega2 = (2 * sp.sin(theta1 - theta2) * (omega1**2 * L1 * (m1 + m2) + g *
(m1 + m2) * sp.cos(theta1) +
                omega2**2 * L2 * m2 * sp.cos(theta1 - theta2))) / \
                (L2 * (2 * m1 + m2 - m2 * sp.cos(2 * theta1 - 2 * theta2)))

    return sp.Matrix([ftheta1, fomega1, ftheta2, fomega2])

r = sp.Matrix([theta1, omega1, theta2, omega2])
f_r = f(r)
J = f_r.jacobian(r)

initial_condition = {
    theta1: np.pi,
    omega1: 0,
    theta2: np.pi,
    omega2: 0,
    L1: 1,
    L2: 1,
    m1: 1,
    m2: 1,
    g: 9.81
}

J_evaluated = J.subs(initial_condition).evalf()
J_numeric = np.array(J_evaluated).astype(np.float64)

eigenvalues, eigenvectors = np.linalg.eig(J_numeric)

```

```
print("Eigenvalues of the Jacobian matrix:")
print(eigenvalues)
```

S4 Data Preparation and Normalization

In order to prepare the data for training and testing our models on, we created two implementations: one for a single initial angle, and one for multiple different initial angles.

After solving the ODE-RK4 solutions for each timestep each and storing the angle measurements θ_1 and θ_2 , we compile all data into a 2D numpy array: the first dimension of the array is for θ_1 , and the second dimension is for θ_2 . For each timestep, there is one array of angles $[\theta_1, \theta_2]$, and for the entire time interval there are $t = \text{timestep}$ arrays of these two angles in one large numpy array.

The code to compile all the data into this two-dimensional array for a single initial angle is as follows.

```
#Save as numpy array (final dataset)
data = np.stack((theta1_points, theta2_points), axis=1)
np.save('pendulum_data.npy', data)

data = np.load('pendulum_data.npy')
```

Figure 4.1 Sample Raw Data (pendulum_data.npy) for one initial angle $[90^\circ, 90^\circ]$

```
Data shape: (1000000, 2)
[[ 9.00000000e+01  9.00000000e+01]
 [ 6.05205306e+01  8.71702674e+01]
 [ 1.66556426e+01  1.91928638e+01]
 ...
 [-1.93928187e-01 -2.74257869e-01]
 [-2.35746381e-02 -3.33385320e-02]
 [ 1.60386422e-01  2.26821076e-01]]
```

We can see that the data is stored in a two-dimensional array (2 for y-shape), with sub arrays for each timestep. In this case, we picked $a = 0$, $b = 1000$, $n = 1000000$ to get 10,000,000

unique timesteps, or sets of $[\theta_1, \theta_2]$ angles. However, our models, especially complex RNNs, are more suited to normalized/scaled data. For this reason, we scale our NumPy array using MinMaxScaler, which scales all numerical values from 0 to 1.

Figure 4.2 Sample Normalized Data for one initial angle $[90^\circ, 90^\circ]$

```
[[0.99586471 1.      ]
 [0.99586292 0.99999948]
 [0.99585756 0.99999792]
 [0.99584862 0.99999532]
 [0.9958361  0.99999167]]
```

In this dataset, we have a two-dimensional array that has 10,000,000 timesteps of data, meaning there are 10,000,000 sets of angles $[\theta_1, \theta_2]$ in the dataset.

For triple pendulum, we also have a two-dimensional array that has 10,000,000 timesteps of data, but each set of angles contains $[\theta_1, \theta_2, \theta_3]$ for each angle of the triple pendulum. Training on data for the triple pendulum took a lot longer than double pendulum due the extra input into the network.

However, to make a dataset that involves multiple different initial angles, we can no longer use a simple 2D numpy array. We need to specify which initial angles have certain data points, so we use a dictionary to depict that.

The key for each element in the dictionary is the initial angle for the data, and the value is the 2D numpy array of time-series data for the pendulum.

Figure 4.3 Sample Normalized Data for multiple angles

```
{'120_0': array([[1.      , 0.53546863],
 [0.99996692, 0.53545478],
 [0.99986769, 0.53541325],
 ...,
 [0.75325428, 0.31489452],
 [0.75200424, 0.31679388],
 [0.75069148, 0.31871432]]), '120_0.1': array([[1.      , 0.53491367],
 [0.99996694, 0.53489986],
 [0.99986778, 0.53485847],
 ...,
 [0.74740153, 0.27597679],
 [0.74642877, 0.2774739 ],
 [0.74539872, 0.27899163]]), '120_0.2': array([[1.      , 0.53434665],
 [0.99996697, 0.53433289],
```

```

[0.99986787, 0.53429164],
...,
[0.73655264, 0.23592428],
[0.73580229, 0.23694166],
[0.73500009, 0.23798078]], '120_0.3': array([[1.      , 0.53376175],
[0.99996699, 0.53374804],
[0.99986797, 0.53370693],
...,
[0.72460711, 0.20343733],
[0.72403619, 0.20397523],
[0.7234174 , 0.20453586]]), '120_0.4': array([[1.      , 0.53315464],
[0.99996702, 0.53314098],
[0.99986808, 0.5331  ],
...,
[0.71957107, 0.18934209],
[0.71924315, 0.18962998],
[0.71886837, 0.1899402 ]]), '120_0.5': array([[1.      , 0.53252269],
[0.99996705, 0.53250907],
[0.9998682 , 0.53246824],
...,

```

In order to train our models on the data, specifically the neural networks, we need to create PyTorch tensors for effective model training. In addition, for multiple different initial angles, we need to feed the data for each initial angle into the model separately, because the models cannot accept dictionaries. Lastly, we need to create input-output arrays for each angle. Sample code for tensor creation and input-output array creation for multiple angle data preparation is given below:

```

# Define the dataset class
class QuadraticDataset(Dataset):
    def __init__(self, x, y):
        self.x = torch.tensor(x, dtype=torch.float32).to(device) # Shape (N, 3)
        self.y = torch.tensor(y, dtype=torch.float32).to(device) # Shape (N, 2)

    def __len__(self):
        return len(self.x)

    def __getitem__(self, idx):
        return self.x[idx], self.y[idx]

data = {}

for i in angles:
    loaded_data = np.load(f'pendulum_data_{str(i[0])}_{str(i[1])}.npz')
    scaler = MinMaxScaler()

```

```

data_ = scaler.fit_transform(loaded_data)
data[f'{str(i[0])}_{str(i[1])}'] = data_

print(data)

def create_io(data):
    x, x_1, x_2, y_1, y_2 = [], [], [], [], []
    for starting in data:
        starting_theta_1_degrees = float(starting.split("_")[0])
        starting_theta_2_degrees = float(starting.split("_")[1])

        starting_theta_1 = starting_theta_1_degrees * pi /180
        starting_theta_2 = starting_theta_2_degrees * pi /180

        angle_data = data[starting]
        for i in range(len(angle_data)):
            x.append(tpoints[i])
            x_1.append(starting_theta_1)
            x_2.append(starting_theta_2)
            y_1.append(angle_data[i][0])
            y_2.append(angle_data[i][1])
    return x, x_1, x_2, y_1, y_2

x, x_1, x_2, y_1, y_2 = create_io(data)

```

We then feed our `x_1` and `x_2` tensors into the neural network, and our output is stored as `y_1` and `y_2` arrays. We use two arrays, one for each angle of the double pendulum. Triple pendulum is similar, but with three angle data tensors instead of two.

S5 Model Training and Performance

S5.1 Sliding Window Approach

The sliding window approach was used to train and test the model at one single initial angle, meaning we would use a simple 2D NumPy array input. The sliding window approach takes in data in sequences of 50 data points (in our case, data points are an array of angle_1 and angle_2 of the pendulum) as training data, and predicts the 51th data point. Once the prediction is completed, another 50 data points are inputted into the model, shifted one data point to the right, so the model would predict the 52st data point.

For example, if the model was given an array of 10,000,000 data points, the first step would be to input the first 0-49 indexes into the model, and predict the 50th index (the 51st data point). In the next iteration, we would input indexes 1-50, and then predict the 51st index (the 52nd data point).

For the sliding window approach, the models were given two features ($\theta_1[]$, $\theta_2[]$), and gave two outputs (θ_1 , θ_2). The models trained with the sliding window approach include: Random Forest Regressor (RF), Multi-Layer Perceptron Regressor (MLPRegressor), Long-Short Term Memory Neural Network (LSTM), Vanilla Recurrent Neural Network (VRNN), BiDirectionalRNN (BIRNN), StackedRNN (STRNN), SGDRRegressor (SGD), Gated Recurrent Network (GRU), Autoregressive Model (AR), and Feed Forward Neural Network (FFNN).

S5.2 Time-step Based Approach

The time-step based approach, unlike the sliding window approach, cannot track time of the datapoint without a 3rd input, the timestep, which is the time at which the angle state of the pendulum is true. With this third input, the model is able to predict the state of the pendulum at any given time, which allows for us to have the model predict the entire motion of the pendulum. In addition, for the time-step based approach, models were trained on multiple different initial angles instead of one initial angle, allowing for more chaos comprehension. The model was then tested on a new initial angle that was “in-between” the trained initial angles (e.g. [120,1], [120,2] trained and [120,1.5] tested). Because the pendulum depends so much on the initial conditions, testing on new initial conditions is the definition of true chaos. Our models were able to predict this chaos, showcasing their power in real world scenarios.

Because we trained on multiple different initial conditions, computing power was not large enough to train on 1000s of data; we had to cut down to 10s of complete pendulum motion for each initial angle to have the best balance of accuracy and computation time.

The model was trained on 80% of the data for each initial angle, and the initial testing on the same initial angle was conducted with the other 20% of the data. After the initial test was done, the model could be used to predict the entire trajectory of the pendulum on any given initial angle for a full 10s of motion. The implementation of the code is below.

```
# Generate predictions for any initial angle
angle = [120.2,0.3]

tpoints = np.arange(a, b, h) # seconds, split into intervals of 100
theta1_points = np.zeros_like(tpoints) # what the first pendulum angle should be
(empty)
theta2_points = np.zeros_like(tpoints) # what the second pendulum angle should be
(empty)
```

```

q = np.array([angle[0]*pi/180, 0, angle[1]*pi/180, 0], float)

for i, t in enumerate(tpoints):
    theta1_points[i] = q[0] * 180 / pi # converted from theta (θ) to degrees (°)
    theta2_points[i] = q[2] * 180 / pi

    k1 = h * f(q, t, L1, L2)
    k2 = h * f(q + 0.5 * k1, t + 0.5 * h, L1, L2)
    k3 = h * f(q + 0.5 * k2, t + 0.5 * h, L1, L2)
    k4 = h * f(q + k3, t + h, L1, L2)
    q += (k1 + 2 * k2 + 2 * k3 + k4) / 6

x_1_unknown = [angle[0]*pi/180]*N
x_2_unknown = [angle[1]*pi/180]*N
x_unknown = tpoints.tolist()
scaler = MinMaxScaler()
y_1_2_unknown = scaler.fit_transform([[a, b] for a, b in zip(theta1_points,
theta2_points)])
y_1_unknown, y_2_unknown = map(list, zip(*y_1_2_unknown))
y_combined = np.vstack([y_1_unknown, y_2_unknown]).T
y_scaled = scaler_y.fit_transform(y_combined)

x_dense_combined = np.vstack([x_1_unknown, x_2_unknown, x_unknown]).T
x_dense_scaled = scaler_x.transform(x_dense_combined)
x_dense_tensor = torch.tensor(x_dense_scaled,
dtype=torch.float32).unsqueeze(1).to(device) # Shape (500, 1, 2)

lstm_model.eval()
with torch.no_grad():
    y_pred_scaled = lstm_model(x_dense_tensor).cpu().numpy()

# Inverse transform predictions
y_pred_unknown = scaler_y.inverse_transform(y_pred_scaled)

# x_1 = initial angle 1 and x_2 is initial angle
# Calculate RMSE and R^2 score
rmse = np.sqrt(mean_squared_error(y_combined, y_pred_unknown))
r2 = r2_score(y_combined, y_pred_unknown)

print(f"RMSE on new angle: {rmse}")
print(f"R^2 Score on new angle: {r2}")

# Plotting
plt.figure(figsize=(12, 6))
plt.plot(x_unknown, y_1_unknown, label='True y_1', color='blue', linestyle='--')
plt.plot(x_unknown, y_2_unknown, label='True y_2', color='green', linestyle='--')

```

```

plt.plot(x_unknown, y_pred_unknown[:, 0], label='Predicted y_1', color='red')
plt.plot(x_unknown, y_pred_unknown[:, 1], label='Predicted y_2', color='orange')
plt.xlabel('x')
plt.ylabel('y')
plt.title('Comparison of True and Predicted Quadratic Curves')
plt.legend()
plt.grid(True)
plt.show()

```

We can then create an animation of the trajectory with predicted pendulum vs actual pendulum

```

import numpy as np
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
from matplotlib.animation import FuncAnimation
from math import sin, cos, pi, floor

from matplotlib import rc
rc('animation', html='jshtml')

def theta_to_xy(theta1, theta2, theta1Len=1, theta2Len=1):
    convert = pi/180
    x1 = sin(theta1*convert) * theta1Len
    y1 = -cos(theta1*convert) * theta1Len
    x2 = x1 + sin(theta2*convert) * theta2Len
    y2 = y1 - cos(theta2*convert) * theta2Len
    return [x1, y1, x2, y2]

x1_points = []
y1_points = []
x2_points = []
y2_points = []

x1_points_p = []
y1_points_p = []
x2_points_p = []
y2_points_p = []

fps = 30
upframe = floor((N/(b-a))/30)

for z in np.arange(0, N, upframe):
    i = int(z)
    preddy = scaler.inverse_transform(y_pred_unknown)
    actual = scaler.inverse_transform(y_1_2_unknown)

    x1, y1, x2, y2 = theta_to_xy(actual[i][0], actual[i][1])
    x1_points.append(x1)
    y1_points.append(y1)
    x2_points.append(x2)
    y2_points.append(y2)

```

```

t1 = preddy[i][0]
t2 = preddy[i][1]

x1p, y1p, x2p, y2p = theta_to_xy(t1, t2)
x1_points_p.append(x1p)
y1_points_p.append(y1p)
x2_points_p.append(x2p)
y2_points_p.append(y2p)

fig = plt.figure(figsize=(5, 4))
L = 2
ax = fig.add_subplot(autoscale_on=False, xlim=(-L, L), ylim=(-L, L))
ax.set_aspect('equal')
ax.grid()

line, = ax.plot([], [], 'o-', lw=2)
trace, = ax.plot([], [], 'r-', lw=1, ms=2, alpha=0.5)
line_p, = ax.plot([], [], 'o-', lw=2)
trace_p, = ax.plot([], [], 'r-', lw=1, ms=2, alpha=0.5)
time_template = 'time = %.1fs'
time_text = ax.text(0.05, 0.9, '', transform=ax.transAxes)

def init():
    line.set_data([], [])
    trace.set_data([], [])
    line_p.set_data([], [])
    trace_p.set_data([], [])
    time_text.set_text('')
    return line, trace, line_p, trace_p, time_text

def update(i):
    thisx = [0, x1_points[i], x2_points[i]]
    thisy = [0, y1_points[i], y2_points[i]]

    history_x = x2_points[:i]
    history_y = y2_points[:i]

    thisx_p = [0, x1_points_p[i], x2_points_p[i]]
    thisy_p = [0, y1_points_p[i], y2_points_p[i]]

    history_x_p = x2_points_p[:i]
    history_y_p = y2_points_p[:i]

    line.set_data(thisx, thisy)
    trace.set_data(history_x, history_y)
    line_p.set_data(thisx_p, thisy_p)
    trace_p.set_data(history_x_p, history_y_p)
    time_text.set_text(time_template % (i * h))
    return line, trace, line_p, trace_p, time_text

ani = FuncAnimation(fig, update, frames=len(np.arange(0, N, upframe)), init_func=init, blit=True,
interval=fps)
print(len(tpoints))
print(tpoints)
plt.close()
ani

```

S6 Results

F. - Friction, N. - New Angle

DPOR (Double Pendulum Old Results)

<i>Model</i>	<i>RMSE</i> (Root Mean Squared Error)	<i>R² score</i>
RF	0.01544513327	0.9856719476
LSTM	5.75E-05	0.9999999457
FFNN	0.010884	1
AR	0.0029	0.9962
SGD	0.009256405799	0.999575681
VRNN	0.006388896611	0.9959306374
GRU	0.0006269770092	0.999992381
BIRNN	0.005670809653	0.9976578647
STRNN	0.005838408014	0.999385092
MLP	0.002479056078	0.999879971

TPOR (Triple Pendulum Old Results)

<i>Model</i>	<i>RMSE</i> (Root Mean Squared Error)	<i>R² score</i>
RF	0.01129455823	1
LSTM	0.00358785945	0.999746585
AR	0.001397030428	0.9999596385
SGD	0.0000117549	0.9999999968
VRNN	0.003843597703	0.9997017647
GRU	0.0001825489016	0.9999993485

DPNR (Double Pendulum New Results)

<i>Model</i>	<i>RMSE</i> (Root Mean Squared Error)	<i>R</i> ² score
LSTM	0.02701026949	0.991527133
FFNN	0.0601	0.9637
AR	0.1414689852	0.7649661836
VRNN	0.10801622193	0.83213767958
GRU	0.03838484786	0.9828663375
BIRNN	0.0401476358	0.9804854312
STRNN	0.0776	0.9272
MLP	0.07547001989	0.9382071728
LSTM F.	0.009545972439	0.9987305659
FFNN F.	0.04352520034	0.9726930857
AR F.	0.1147081118	0.813996658
VRNN F.	0.01498100339	0.9968600989
GRU F.	0.01495750004	0.9968525695
BIRNN F.	0.02151495112	0.9934850374
STRNN F.	0.03889751223	0.9787433817
MLP F.	0.02355786199	0.992256693
LSTM F. N.	0.01526276704	0.9966306085
FFNN F. N.	0.03135922906	0.9856980934

AR F. N.	0.07867807164	0.9096737697
VRNN F. N.	0.01662786637	0.9959721216
GRU F. N.	0.01812534783	0.9952500725
BIRNN F. N.	0.01790802388	0.99532312
STRNN F. N.	0.02916268921	0.9876285733
MLP F. N.	0.02255682877	0.9925944279
LSTM F. N.	0.01526276704	0.9966306085

TPNR (Triple Pendulum New Results)

<i>Model</i>	<i>RMSE (Root Mean Squared Error)</i>	<i>R² score</i>
LSTM	0.0217483668	0.9926426858
FFNN	0.111988	0.804925
AR	0.01928107782	0.9946454085
VRNN	0.08616199945	0.8900889747
GRU	0.02194231324	0.99251926601
BIRNN	0.05950567576	0.9425891494
STRNN	0.1101345678	0.8270633157
MLP	0.08392586826	0.8890615657
LSTM F.	0.01081907444	0.9974589887
FFNN F.	0.01887	0.992468
AR F.	0.09654626626	0.7957978087

GRU F.	0.009112483033	0.998233013
MLP F.	0.0440676335	0.970510905
BRNN F.	0.01729901543	0.9937292637
VRNN F.	0.02435479116	0.9873772535
SRNN F.	0.02374870839	0.9884793623
LSTM F. N.	0.008165150712	0.9985423666
FFNN F. N.	0.02404562523	0.9873630177
AR F. N.	0.09074171863	0.8137404905
VRNN F. N.	0.006497543656	0.9990931847
GRU F. N.	0.01654486026	0.9940054658
BIRNN F. N.	0.01821819038	0.9923983602
STRNN F. N.	0.02120998862	0.9902851500
MLP F. N.	0.02965704869	0.9812044878

S7 Glossary

Machine learning: a field of artificial intelligence (AI) that allows computers to learn and improve from data without being explicitly programmed

Deep learning: a subset of machine learning that focuses on utilizing neural networks to perform tasks such as classification, regression, and representation learning

Time series data: a collection of data points recorded at regular intervals of time

Neural network: a method in artificial intelligence (AI) that teaches computers to process data in a way that is inspired by the human brain

Multi-pendulum system: a physical system that consists of multiple pendulums attached together

Chaotic system: systems whose behavior is highly sensitive to initial conditions

Synthetic data: artificial data that is created to mimic the structure and properties of real-world data

Double pendulum: a pendulum with another pendulum attached to its end

Implicit iterative differential equation: a differential equation where the relationship between the unknown function and its derivatives is not explicitly stated

Runge Kutta Method for 4th Order Differential Equations: a family of implicit and explicit iterative methods, which include the Euler method, used in temporal discretization for the approximate solutions of simultaneous nonlinear equations

Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE): a performance indicator for regression models

R-squared (R²): a statistical measure in a regression model that determines the proportion of variance in the dependent variable that can be explained by the independent variable

Step size: a configurable hyperparameter that determines the magnitude of the update to machine learning models during training

Sequential (model): a model that inputs or outputs sequences of data

Supervised (model): a machine learning algorithm that uses labeled data sets to learn the relationship between input and output data

Lyapunov exponent: quantity that characterizes the rate of separation of infinitesimally close trajectories

Eigenvalues: a set of scalars associated with a linear system of equations

MinMaxScaler: scales the data to a fixed range, typically between 0 and 1

Adam Optimizer: an optimization algorithm used in machine learning to train deep neural networks

Learning rate regulator: regulates the learning rate (the speed at which models learn)

Overfitting: when a model is too closely trained to a specific data set, causing it to make inaccurate predictions on new data

stacked NumPy array: multiple arrays joined along a new axis

Tensor: a fundamental data type in artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning that are used to represent and manipulate data

SciKit Learn: an open source machine learning library

Sliding window: a technique that involves analyzing a segment of data at a time while moving the analysis window

Jacobian matrix: a matrix containing all the first-order partial derivatives of a vector-valued function

Undamped oscillator: a system that vibrates without any resistive or damping forces acting upon it

Phase portrait: a geometric representation of the orbits of a dynamical system in the phase plane

Gradient descent: an optimization algorithm used to train machine learning models by minimizing errors between predicted and actual results